

Extensions of POMCP Planning and Applications to Robotic and Cyber-physical Systems

Alberto Castellini, Enrico Marchesini, Giulio Mazzi,
Federico Bianchi, Maddalena Zuccotto and Alessandro Farinelli
Dept. Computer Science, Verona University
Email: name.surname@univr.it

Abstract—We present recent results related to extensions and applications of Partially Observable Monte Carlo Planning to real-world problems involving robotic and cyber-physical systems. Experiments were performed in the context of two projects: "Dipartimenti di Eccellenza 2018-22", Italian Ministry of Education, Universities and Research, and "Safe Place: Sistemi IoT per ambienti di vita salubri e sicuri", POR FESR 2014-20. Three main research lines are developed. The first concerns the explanation and monitoring of POMCP policies by integrating symbolic and non-symbolic approaches. The second regards the applicability of POMCP to real robotic scenarios. The third concerns POMCP policy improvement and adaptation.

Index Terms—POMDP, POMCP, Safety, Policy adaptation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Planning in a partially observable environment is an important problem in artificial intelligence and robotics. A popular framework to model such problem is *Partially Observable Markov Decision Processes (POMDPs)* [1], [4] that combine the strengths of Hidden Markov Models and Markov Decision Processes, by capturing dynamics that depend on both unobserved states and effects of sequential decisions. A pioneering algorithm for synthesizing POMDP policies is *Partially Observable Monte-Carlo Planning (POMCP)* [2], [12] which uses a particle filter to represent the belief and a Monte-Carlo Tree Search based strategy to compute the policy online. These tools allow to scale to very large application domains and they have recently been used to solve hard problems in Artificial Intelligence (AI), such as playing complex games [11]. In the next three sections we present recent results on three research lines related to extensions and applications of POMCP to real-world scenarios involving autonomous robotic and cyber-physical systems.

II. MONITORING POMCP SAFETY

XPOMCP, a methodology developed in the context of the project "Dipartimenti di Eccellenza 2018-2022", implements a mechanism for generating human-understandable descriptions of POMCP policies [7], [8]. A human expert first provides qualitative information, in the form of logical formulas, on a property of the system, enriched with an indication of the expected behavior of the system in specific situations (e.g., "the robot should move fast if it is highly confident that the path is not cluttered, I expect this level of confidence to be

Fig. 1. Shielding decisions with XPOMCP [8].

above 90%"). The approach, displayed in Figure 1, analyzes a set of execution traces and computes the parameters of logical formulas by analyzing the execution of the system (e.g., "the robot moves fast if its confidence of being in an uncluttered segment is at least 93.4%"). The approach formalizes the problem of parameter computation as a *MAX-SMT* problem which allows to express complex logical formulas and to compute optimal assignments when the template is not fully satisfiable. This quantitative answer is then used to build a shield, a safety mechanism that forces the planner to satisfy the constraints expressed by the expert. The shield works alongside the Monte-Carlo Tree Search, by preemptively blocking some actions that, according to the rules, should not be selected in specific situations. The shield is also enriched with a mechanism that quantifies how much the current belief is far from satisfying the rules. This allows extra flexibility in filtering the beliefs accepted by the shield, an important requirement for real-time algorithms working with partial knowledge.

To empirically evaluate the performance of the shield, we tested it in two domains, namely, the well-known *Tiger* problem and a robotic problem in which a mobile platform must move as fast as possible in a cluttered environment avoiding collisions. To test the robustness of the shield mechanism, we inject an error into POMCP by wrongly setting one of its parameters. This error subtly affects the decisions of the policy keeping almost unchanged the average performance but considering some decisions non-optimal and therefore unexpected by experts (i.e., unsafe). Experiments show that the shielding mechanism can improve performance while using a compact and expressive representation of expected properties. The use of the shield degrades performance only negligibly.

* Email: name.surname@univr.it

III. POMCP FOR MOBILE ROBOT NAVIGATION

Autonomous mobile robots employed in industrial applications often operate in complex and uncertain environments. In the context of the project "Dipartimenti di Eccellenza 2018-2022" we have recently proposed an approach based on an extension of POMCP for robot velocity regulation in industrial-like environments characterized by uncertain motion difficulties [3]. The velocity selected by POMCP is used by a Deep Reinforcement Learning engine controller which deals with path planning. This two-layer planning approach, displayed in Figure 2, allows POMCP to exploit prior knowledge on the relationships between task similarities to improve performance in terms of time spent to traverse a path with obstacles. We also propose three measures to support human-understanding of the strategy used by POMCP to improve the performance.

The overall architecture is tested on a Turtlebot3 in two environments, a rectangular path and a realistic production line in a research lab. Tests performed on a C++ simulator confirm the capability of the proposed approach to profitably use prior knowledge, achieving a performance improvement from 0.7% to 3.1% depending on the complexity of the path. Experiments on a Unity simulator show that the proposed two-layer approach outperforms also single-layer approaches based only on the engine controller (i.e., without the POMCP layer). In this case the performance improvement is up to 37% comparing to a state-of-the-art deep reinforcement learning engine controller, and up to 51% comparing to the standard ROS engine controller. Finally, experiments in a real-world testing arena confirm the possibility to run the approach on real robots.

Fig. 2. Two-layer planning approach [3].

IV. POLICY ADAPTATION FOR AIR QUALITY CONTROL

Air quality is very important for human health. The global emergency related to COVID-19 pandemic has also increased the importance of this problem since the virus transmission

has been proved to have positive correlation to air pollution [6]. In the context of the Safe Place project we are developing control strategies based on POMCP to control air conditioning (i.e., thermal comfort) and sanification in indoor environments. From sensors we monitor temperature and relative humidity, volatile organic compound (VOC), carbon dioxide (CO₂), ozone (O₃), particulates (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀); then we predict (or assume to know) the amount of people in the environment in the next hours. Using this information our planner suggests optimal control actions for actuators. The methodological aspect of greatest interest in this project is policy adaptability and improvement. The goal is to produce a planner that initially uses prior knowledge about the environment (e.g., dynamics and sensor models) provided by experts and then adapts the control strategy by learning online the true dynamics of the environment and sensor models. This goal could be reached by integrating model-based and model-free planning methods and using policy improvement strategies [5].

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research is partially funded by project "Dipartimenti di Eccellenza 2018-2022", Italian Ministry of Education, Universities and Research, and Safe Place - Sistemi IoT per ambienti di vita salubri e sicuri, POR FESR 2014-2020.

REFERENCES

- [1] K.J. Åström, "Optimal control of Markov processes with incomplete state information", *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, 10(1), pp. 174-205, (1965).
- [2] A. Castellini, G. Chalkiadakis, and A. Farinelli. Influence of State-Variable Constraints on Partially Observable Monte Carlo Planning, 28th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI 2019), pages 5540-5546, 2019.
- [3] A. Castellini, E. Marchesini, A. Farinelli. Partially Observable Monte Carlo Planning with state variable constraints for mobile robot navigation. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, Elsevier, 104:104382, 2021
- [4] L.P. Kaelbling, M.L. Littman, A.R. Cassandra, "Planning and Acting in Partially Observable Stochastic Domains", *Artificial Intelligence*, 101(1-2), pp. 99-134 (1998).
- [5] R. Laroche, P. Trichelair, R. Tachet. Safe Policy Improvement with Baseline Bootstrapping. *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Machine Learning*, PMLR 97, pp. 3652-3661, 2019.
- [6] S. Lolli, Y.C. Chen, S.H. Wang, G. Vivone, "Impact of meteorological conditions and air pollution on COVID-19 pandemic transmission in Italy", *Scientific Reports* 10, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-73197-8>, (2020).
- [7] G. Mazzi, A. Castellini, A. Farinelli. "Identification of unexpected decisions in Partially Observable Monte Carlo Planning: a rule-based approach". 20th International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems (AAMAS 2021), pp. 889-89 (2021).
- [8] G. Mazzi, A. Castellini, A. Farinelli. "Rule-based shielding for Partially Observable Monte-Carlo Planning". 31st International Conference on Automated Planning and Scheduling (ICAPS 2021), pp. 243-251 (2021).
- [9] S. Ross, J. Pineau, S. Paquet, B. Chaib-draa, "Online planning algorithms for POMDPs", *CoRR*, (2014).
- [10] S. Russell, P. Norvig, "Artificial Intelligence: A modern approach", Prentice Hall, 3edn. (2010).
- [11] J. Schrittwieser, I. Antonoglou, T. Hubert, K. Simonyan, L. Sifre, S. Schmitt, A. Guez, E. Lockhart, D. Hassabis, T. Graepel, T. Lillicrap, D. Silver, "Mastering atari, go, chess and shogi by planning with a learned model", *Nature* 588(7839), pp. 604-609 (2020).
- [12] D. Silver, J. Veness, "Monte-Carlo Planning in large POMDPs", *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 23 (NIPS 2010), 2164-2172, (2010).